

Short Communication

OF CLAIM

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Abstract

A mundane person claims always both legal and illegal share. He is interested more to get other person's share. He states that his share is of his own. Also other person's share is his own. Thus he is the owner of the whole property. A divine person never claims anything. Divinity paves the way to be free from any mundane belonging that poisons life.

Key words: Claim, assertion, demand, request, due, right, challenge

Introduction

Creative writing is based more on manifestation rather than on expression. It does not inform, rather it reveals. So it bears no reference. The best creative writing is critical, and the best critical writing is creative. This article is an outcome of thinking about creative writing meant for a general readership. As such, I have adopted a free style methodology so that everyone can enjoy the pleasure of reading. As you might know, Francis Bacon (1561-1626), the immortal essayist, wrote many essays namely 'Of Love', 'Of Friendship', 'Of Ambition', 'Of Studies', and so on. The multiple-minded genius correctly pointed out that all the words of the dictionary can be used as themes for essays. But little has been done since his death to continue or finish his monumental task. Bacon's unique individual style of presentation ignited my imagination and encouraged me to write creative essays as a method of relieving a wide range of emotions through catharsis.

ARTICLE

Claim is an assertion that something is true, typically without providing evidence or proof. For example: He was dogged by the claim that he had CIA links.

It is a demand or request for something considered one's due. For example: If no one claims the items, they will become Crown property.

It is a right to something. For example: The bank has a claim on their house.

It is an assertion open to challenge e.g., a claim of authenticity; advertisers' extravagant claims.

In an ideal state claim is absent. Here all happen or are received automatically without any persuasion. In real life it happens never. As such claim is omnipresent everywhere in every age.

The greatest example of claim is observed in case of a baby. Mother does not give milk to her baby unless it cries. A child cries just to draw attention. Here cry and claim are identical. However, man learns the utility of claim just with the beginning of heart throb.

There are two types of feeding viz., time feeding and demand feeding. Earlier, the traditional mothers would practise time feeding. Modern mothers practise demand feeding. Both are strategies. Both are used as per situation.

In case of time feeding claim has no function. Mother feeds her child as per fixed schedule whether it is required or not it matters nothing. Mother moves being driven by emotion more than demand. The baby takes food if it is hungry, otherwise it declines. An affectionate mother tries forcefully to feed the babe and the babe vomits the taken food. Then the affectionate mother stops her venture.

Such a serious mother frequently goes to the doctor claiming that the intake of her baby is very little or negligible. In medical science there is no lesson that confirms the satisfaction of mother regarding consumption of food by the children. As such they say care is good but over care is too bad. Everybody knows it except the affectionate mother. Generally, hardly a mother can distinguish between affection and indulgence.

If an honest person gets something of third party then he readily returns back that thing to the concerned owner. He thus proves his honesty, transparency and solvency of mind. In contrast a dishonest person never returns the thing to the owner. He considers and claims it as his own. Then the genuine owner either has to pay money or apply force or go to the court to get back his belongings.

He who has sufficient proof then he does not claim. He simply submits the relevant papers to the competent authority. He simply states, "Paper will speak". In the court vague claim is not considered only concrete document is required in support of any claim.

There are two types of persons. The first category claims credit without doing anything. The second category claims no recognition. He serves silently without any reciprocation or expectation. He is a Good Samaritan. Both are diagonally opposite in their philosophy towards their lives.

A dishonest person takes his own share first. Then he claims additional amount. If he gets it then being allured he claims further the whole amount as his own. He holds it forcefully. He is either intelligent or bold or both simultaneously. Similarly, a fool also claims the whole share. Since he is fool and weak in all respect he cannot keep it in his custody. In contrast a wise never claims additional or illegal share as his own.

A mundane person claims always both legal and illegal share. He is interested more to get other person's share. He states that his share is of his own. Also other person's share is his own. Thus he is the owner of the whole property. A divine person never claims anything. Divinity paves the way to be free from any mundane belonging that poisons life.

A sly person always claims. He receives his own share. Yet he claims additional share. It is his habit. He is envious of fortune of others. He wants to be the owner of anything of his choice by hook or by crook i.e., by any means fair or foul. To get it he requests first. If he does not get it then he applies force. If he even does not get it then he steals it. Sometimes he escapes from watching or suspicion. Sometimes he is caught re-handed. He is beaten black and blue. Yet he does not change his habit of stealing. As such they say, "Habit is the second nature".

A judicious person claims on genuine ground. In contrast a fool claims without any valid reason. People respect a wise person. The learned never speaks rubbish. A fool has no such cautiousness. He gets no respect. He seldom bothers to achieve it.

The word of wise is authentic. He never argues basing on baseless fallacy. His word is law. His sayings have weightage. For this he can claim appreciation. But he never claims name and fame. Both name and fame give birth to pride. The learned knows that, "Pride goes before a fall". As such the wise is quite indifferent on these mundane affairs.

He who claims absurd thing becomes a laughing stock. None laughs for him. Rather everybody laughs at him. Someone rectifies his attitude. The

other one amends his behavior never. Here education and culture help to correct someone. The most interesting point is to note that sometimes those factors influence very little or never at all. The reasons are unknown. It is quite a grey area.

Absurd thinking and abstract thinking are identical. Both the claims originated from these two sources are based on imagination. Imagination obeys no rule. It loves democracy. As such it moves in any direction, as per its sweet will, just like a bird that flies in the sky in any direction without any obstruction. Imagination is tender in nature. The paradox is that in spite of being tender it can break and really it breaks all barriers and crosses all boundaries with its violent force in reality.

Someone claims with proof. Someone claims without proof. Both the persons are diagonally opposite in their attitudes. For claim if there remains no punishment then the number of claims are infinite in numbers. Punishments act as brake and are of two types viz., economical or physical. Sometimes it may be imposed either of the two or both simultaneously judging the nature of activity of the offender. Also punishment depends upon the discretion of the judge. The paradox is that same judge differs in judgment for the identical breach of law by different persons.

CONCLUSION

If claim is genuine then there lies no problem. In case of absurd or illegal claim it invites danger and culminates into mishap. Boundary dispute among nations invites war. In case of triangular love claim of love of the contesting lovers, over a single heart, never becomes fruitful but creates distance that causes lifelong disturbance coupled with unbearable pain. Only the bearer knows where the shoe pinches.

REFERENCES

No reference, since the present article is an outcome of Creative Nonfiction Writing.

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